

Problem-based learning (PBL) implemented in Manufacturing Processes

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Abstract

Manufacturing processes course is one of the compulsory subject for industrial engineering course. Problem Based Learning (PBL) implemented into traditional teaching methods. The study indicates that PBL may be an effective complementary method for manufacturing processes. Students need opportunities to practice the newly acquired skills. Before class, rather than beginning with a single question that is multilayered and complex, use a sequence of questions to build knowledge. The paper elaborates approaches to daily products selection and unites to acquire knowledge, self-studying, group discussion and presentation. Class discussion provides an appropriate opportunity to give knowledge in depth. The possibility of offering the students and the efficiency of PBL were also evaluated and discussed.

Keywords: Problem based learning; PBL; Manufacturing Processes; Industrial Engineering.

1 Introduction

It has been many years for Thai education to support project-based learning (PBL) to succeed their education goals. PBL offers the different educational strategies that are not same as the traditional lecture. Barrows and Tamblyn (1980) published their study on abilities of medical students after trials with new learning and teaching styles. The PBL enhance learning by activate students to work in teams and solve problems together, while developing contents knowledge, idea, reasoning, and interpersonal skills (Jones et al., 2013). Moreover, the involvement with problem-solving also helps to keep students interest in course contents, that they are learning skills needed to be successful in the field (White, 2001; Hmelo-Silver, 2004; Dahms and Stentoft, 2008). Since its emergence within the engineering education, a growing interest in using PBL has been noticed, which is aligned with current efforts to move from decontextualized presentation of technical content to holistic integration of content and practice (Sheppard et al., 2008). Despite an increasing number of literature evidence, a limited number of researchers has provided systematic studies of PBL (Galand et al., 2012)

Manufacturing Processes course is an undergraduate course designed to provide the basic skills and knowledge in the areas of manufacturing processes & materials and is part of the core mechanical engineering curriculum (Zhou & Donaldson, 2010). Unlike other math-based engineering courses. Consequently, the students may not be able to see the connection and may lose interest in learning the subject {Manu}. So, PBL has a correspondence to gain experience from learning by themselves (Dewey, 1938). Thammasat School of Engineering (TSE) is a young engineering program in its 2nd year. The manufacturing process is being taught for Industrial Engineering and Mechanical Engineering course. A field trip has been included for this course. For practical, students and teacher are able to bridge the gap between what's been taught in the classroom and what's been practiced on the manufacturing floor.

1.1 Manufacturing Processes Course

Learning and understanding Manufacturing Processes aids our understanding of the world and all around us. Manufacturing Processes phenomena can be described at multiple levels of representation which are interconnected and related in terms of information. There are three levels of Manufacturing Processes representations, namely the Create for example casting, modify (machining, forming) and assembly (Welding, fitting) (Mikell P. Groover, 2010). This course provides the student with an introduction to industrial manufacturing from the viewpoint of mechanical technology. Successful completion of the course will provide the student with the benefits, limitations, and applications of different machine tools and engineering materials

for product manufacturing. Manufacturing process engineering came from the technological development and profound change of the steel industry. Adaptability of machinery to a variety of manufacturing processes is studied. Each process is covered from a technical perspective; correct terms are introduced so that the student will be able to use the language of the engineer or technologist.

The students completing this course will be able to:

- Describe basic materials properties, behaviours, and failure modes and their relevance to manufacturing processes.
- Describe basic physical and mechanical properties (emphasis metals), behaviours, and failure modes and their relevance to manufacturing processes.
- Determine the interrelationships between thermal, elastic, and strength properties and their influence on manufacturing costs, efficiency, and quality.
- Describe basic heat treating methods for metals and their purposes.
- Describe selected metal forming operations and calculate the associated force and energy requirements.
- Select appropriate coating and surface enhancement processes, and understand their limitations.
- Evaluate the forces associated with standard machining, turning, and grinding operations.
- Describe molding and casting processes for metals.
- Describe manufacturing processes for powder metal alloys.
- Understand basic product design and manufacturability.
- Understand different machining operations Traditional manufacturing (Milling, turning, grinding) and non-traditional manufacturing (EDM, ECM, Laser, water Jet and others) and describe various machineries

During the last phase of the project, the student is asked to identify a manufacturing issue associated with the chosen process and/or material, conduct research on the issue, provide a solution to the resolution of the issue, write a report on the work, and present the work to the class. Surveys are conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of the approach. It is expected that by letting student choose their own manufacturing topic, the students will be more motivated to learn and learn more effectively.

2 Classroom Implementation

At the present, course syllabus was distributed to all students. All students read by themselves and picked their topics based on their interest and stated why they are interested in the particular manufacturing process. For introduction, we discuss about the topics that we are going to focus. The first case, using the PBL to brainstorm. The case study is as follows: "A young industrial engineer works in a company that want to launch coffee product which guarantees to awaken your sober morning and get you ready for the chaotic day in the city. Design container considered marketing concept. Packaging plays a pivotal role in the branding process of the product, attracting customers and providing customers what they're looking for when they take the product home" Figure 1 shows types for coffee's containers.

Figure 1. Types of containers.

2.1 Investigating/ Discussion problem

The students make grouped and seat together to discuss the problem. They were grouped for 4-5 students, refine their lists. It was starting by listing down each fact from the problem statement. lists of FACTS (what we know), IDEAS (related thoughts and hypotheses), LEARNING ISSUES (what we need to know more about), and ACTIONS (what we need to do), noted their thoughts both on 1 sheet of A4 paper. They noted information through their own exploration of the resources, and they discuss findings with their group members to compile the growing list of evidence that will form the basis of their argument in the final group presentation. Any ideas related to the problem and ideas were generated and summarized by each member and noted down. Then they will discuss learning issues that can help them to solve the problem. Finally, they search for information from every resource including books, journal, notes, using internet. All of these processes were listed in FILA table as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. FILA

Facts	Ideas	Learning Outcomes (Issues)	Actions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There are many choices for container for Coffee. - What are the differences between plastic, glass and metal for manufacturing processes? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Needs experiences and general knowledge. - Needs to share the information with the other participants. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How it's made? -What are challenges and benefits of each manu-facturing processes? -What are the cost for manufacturing processes? -What are the concepts of teaching and learning in this course? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Finding information on the internet about each manu-facturing. - Do the discussion with all the group members. - Finish the assign-ment before the deadline.

During the classroom discussion and group sharing, students rarely add on additional points from other groups or edit their work during the classroom discussion. During discussion, the teacher noticed that many students are more self-centered, they only focus on completing their own tasks and do not care about others' ideas. The students' work and the teacher's description matched the classroom observation. The students want to finish the assignment which students but not to listen to other groups sharing. The first group initially listed all coffee's packaging in the market. They pointed sustainable packaging, which might be not involved with our topics. They can explain some manufacturing processes for Example, blow molding for PET. For this chance, we checked basic knowledge for Material sciences that they passed last semester. Teacher discussed all group for materials for deep drawing process of soft drink vessel. Some students confused aluminum, stainless steel, and steel coated by tin. For this time, they have to carry the real part, magnetic checking and discuss their properties. The final points showed that the student started to realize relationship between materials & manufacturing processes and cost for manufacturing and that they have known from experience. This might occur during final discussion and noted to the FILA table before presentation. After finished presentation, we discussed about EG (Electro Galvanized Steel Sheet) and GI (Hot Dipped Galvanized Steel). This topic we will study in this course after midterm examination under surface treatment. However, there was no attempt shown in making corrections or indications. The teacher had explicitly discussed about phase diagram that they have already passes and confused about austenite phase and magnetic properties. Thus, it can be explained that the student might intently wrote idea from their experiences and researches. Therefore, for future lessons, it is recommended to use the FILA chart in the landscape orientation. Both students show misunderstandings for some basic background. This can be related back to the inaccurate explanation by the teacher during the first phase. Students filled up this idea by answering the teacher's question: "Rust can corrode the steel., What are the chemicals in the equation? Why does not stainless steel rust." The teacher's unprepared state had caused students' misconception, it also reflects students understanding of theory and their behaviour during class discussion. In PBL, students should also learn to be a good listener in addition to being an active speaker.

Before final examination, several videos on manufacturing were created for normal people as a learning resource and freely shared via YouTube. The videos were assigned for students to practice replacing fieldtrip. Teacher started the case study with How It's Made for LPG cylinder tank. Unfortunately, students cannot see the real part in classroom. They were assigned to investigate by themselves at home or canteen. The student must draft manufacturing processes chart, start from raw steel sheet to finish product. The students utilized innovative way, such as video from YouTube to present the subject content and demonstrated their research

capability and present their project. Figure 2 shows example for Incredible gas cylinders manufacturing process from YouTube. The students were asked to find out cycle time and production time for 1 tank on the production line and also they were asked to find out other manufacturing methods in order to replace producing for the same product.

Figure 2. Example for Incredible gas cylinders manufacturing process.
(Source : <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=U7Vj5-Z8wD8>)

It is worth noting that the focus of finding production times in order to confirm the student’s knowledge for name the processes. Presentation helps this happen by allowing the students to interact with their friends and teacher. In order to find other manufacturing processes created thinking through ideas and making them approachable as product. Throughout the discussion after presentation, the students were given opportunities to express their opinion, reflect on their ideas and learn from them.

3 Teaching Evaluation

The teaching evaluation used the questionnaire with the 5-point Likert scale to gather level of satisfaction about PBL in this course on students’ opinions. The questionnaire distributed to all students (55 students), 31 of questionnaires were collected. The evaluation criteria range from 5 (strongly satisfied) to 1 (strongly dissatisfied). Mean scores are interpreted with regard to the satisfaction level as follow:

- 4.50 – 5.00 means strongly satisfied
- 3.50 – 4.49 means very satisfied
- 2.50 – 3.49 means weakly satisfied
- 1.50 – 2.49 means dissatisfied
- 1.00 – 1.49 means strongly dissatisfied

Table 2. Level of satisfaction about PBL in this course

	N (Number of participants)				
strongly satisfied	3				
very satisfied	9				
weakly satisfied	14				
dissatisfied	2				
strongly dissatisfied	3				
Total	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	S.D.
	31	1	5	3.22	1.05

As can be from the table 2, most of students (14 students or 45.2%) were weakly satisfied. Only 3 students or 9.7% were strongly satisfied and also 3 students were strongly dissatisfied. As the result, we can say that the students were weakly satisfied for satisfaction about PBL in this course (Mean=3.22 and S.D.=1.05). At the end of the questionnaire, open-ended question asked about feeling for PBL in this course. A student raised

comments: “PBL should be taught by experienced lecturers, the PBL was not suited for many students, our lecturer cannot handle all students. Only 2-3 students could understand that teacher taught.”

Not surprisingly, students were treated familiar with the equation on traditional math-based engineering course with the traditional passive lecture. So, students feel the much difference of responses between the two courses. While passively familiar traditional math-based engineering course, students may like to individually study and practice for exercises. For manufacturing course, they have to find out idea, practice skill, thinking process and made their project presentations. Some of them suggested that the topic of their interest really helped them to learn but it is out of syllabus which were not found in the exam paper.

4 Conclusion

Problem-based learning (PBL) was implemented to Industrial and Mechanical engineering students via teaching for Manufacturing processes. Students involved in problem-based learning acquire knowledge. This technique stimulates learning in problem-solving contexts, active learning and team participation. Some soft skill was practiced among the students such as leadership, interpersonal and self-directed learning skill. They are also trained to be punctual, actively generating creative ideas and good motivator to the friends.

As the results, the following recommendations are made for future. Our classroom discussion is less than that of course planning. Its overall effectiveness needs to be further evaluated with more samples. Teacher should improve teaching practice. The ways for improving may include technology. The explosion of connection in our culture due to technology has been nothing short of amazing. Because many students and different basic knowledge. It should divide to small group with the same knowledge level. Imagine for practices form clip VDO may extend to special guests and field trips. (Brian Gatén, 2020).

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